

THE BASIC WAYS OF WORD FORMATION IN MODERN ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6543376>

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Annotation: *The aim of the article is the basic ways of word formation in modern English and giving instruction to young learners different easy ways of translation.*

Keywords: *compounding forms, blending, nonnative, rhyming compounds, affixation, derivation, clipping, acronyms, unchallenging, reanalysis, analogy, occur, subjective, objective, mailman, historical materials, visible, possessive, productive results.*

Abstract. In modern English there are different types of word formation. Indeed such kind of word formations help in making sentences. They are:

Compounding Compounding forms a word out of two or more root morphemes. The words are called compounds or compound words. In Linguistics, compounds can be either native or borrowed. Native English roots are typically free morphemes, so that means native compounds are made out of independent words that can occur by themselves. Examples: *mailman* (composed of free root *mail* and free root *man*) *mail carrier dog house fireplace fireplug* (a regional word for 'fire hydrant') *fire hydrant*

Rhyming compounds (subtype of compounds) These words are compounded from two rhyming words. Examples: *love-dovey chiller-killer* There are words that are formally very similar to rhyming compounds, but are not quite compounds in English because the second element is not really a word--it is just a nonsense item added to a root word to form a rhyme. Examples: *higgledy-piggledy tootsie-wootsie* This formation process is associated in English with child talk (and talk addressed to children), technically called hypocoristic language. Examples: *bunnie-wunnie Henny Penny*

Derivation Derivation is the creation of words by modification of a root without the addition of other roots. Often the effect is a change in part of speech.

Affixation (Subtype of Derivation) The most common type of derivation is the addition of one or more affixes to a root, as in the

word *derivation* itself. This process is called affixation, a term which covers both prefixation and suffixation.

Blending Blending is one of the most beloved of word formation processes in English. It is especially creative in that speakers take two words and merge them based not on morpheme structure but on sound structure. The resulting words are called blends.

Usually in word formation we combine roots or affixes along their edges: one morpheme comes to an end before the next one starts. For example, we form *derivation* out of the sequence of morphemes de+riv+at(e)+ion. One morpheme follows the next and each one has identifiable boundaries. The morphemes do not overlap.

Clipping Clipping is a type of abbreviation of a word in which one part is 'clipped' off the rest, and the remaining word now means essentially the same thing as what the whole word means or meant. For example, the word *rifle* is a fairly modern clipping of an earlier compound *rifle gun*, meaning a gun with a rifled barrel. (*Rifled* means having a spiral groove causing the bullet to spin, and thus making it more accurate.) Another clipping is *burger*, formed by clipping off the beginning of the word *hamburger*. (This clipping could only come about once *hamburg+er* was reanalyzed as *ham+burger*.)

Acronyms Acronyms are formed by taking the initial letters of a phrase and making a word out of it. Acronyms provide a way of turning a phrase into a word. The classical acronym is also pronounced as a word. *Scuba* was formed from *self-contained underwater breathing apparatus*. The word *snafu* was originally WW2 army slang for Situation Normal All Fucked Up. NOW (National Organization of Women) US or U.S., USA or U.S.A. (United States) UN or U.N. (United Nations) IMF (International Monetary Fund)

Reanalysis Sometimes speakers unconsciously change the morphological boundaries of a word, creating a new morph or making an old one unrecognizable. This happened in *hamburger*, which was originally *Hamburger steak* 'chopped and formed steak in the Hamburg style, then *hamburger* (*hamburg + er*), then *ham + burger*

Folk etymology A popular idea of a word's origin that is not in accordance with its real origin.

Many folk etymologies are cases of reanalysis in which the word is not only reanalysis but it changes under the influence of the new understanding of its morphemes. The result is that speakers think it has a different origin than it does.

Analogy Sometimes speakers take an existing word as a model and form other words using some of its morphemes as a fixed part, and changing one of them to something new, with an analogically similar meaning. *Cheeseburger* was formed on the analogy of *hamburger*, replacing a perceived morpheme *ham* with *cheese*. *carjack* and *skyjack* were also formed by analogy.

Novel creation In novel creation, a speaker or writer forms a word without starting from other morphemes. It is as if the word is formed out of 'whole cloth', without reusing any parts.

Some examples of now-conventionalized words that were novel creations include *blimp*, *googol* (the mathematical term), *bling*, and possibly *slang*, which emerged in the last 200 years with no obvious etymology. Some novel creations seem to display 'sound symbolism', in which a word's phonological form suggests its meaning in some way. For example, the sound of the word *bling* seems to evoke heavy jewelry making noise. Another novel creation whose sound seems to relate to its meaning is *badonkadonk*, 'female rear end', a reduplicated word which can remind English speakers of the repetitive movement of the rear end while walking.

Creative respelling Sometimes words are formed by simply changing the spelling of a word that the speaker wants to relate to the new word. Product names often involve creative respelling, such as *Mr. Kleen*.

REFERENCES:

1. Lingvisticheskiy Entsiklopedicheskiy Slovar'. [1990] 2002. Moskva: Sovetskaya Entsiklope-
2. diya.
3. Longman Dictionary of Phrasal Verbs. 1983. Harlow, UK: Longman.
4. Skujin, a, Valentīna. (ed.). 2007. Valodniecības pamatterminu skaidrojums
5. Boyd, Richard. [1979] 1998. Metaphor and theory change: What is "metaphor" a me-
6. taphor for? In Metaphor and Thought. Ortony, Andrew (ed.). Cambridge: Cam-
7. bridge University Press. 481–532.
8. Boase-Beier, Jean. 2006. Stylistic Approaches to Translation: Translation Theories Explored.

9. Manchester: St Jerome Publishing.
10. Boers, Frank. 1999. When a bodily source domain becomes prominent: The joy of
11. counting metaphors in the socio-economic domain. In: Metaphor in Cognitive
12. Linguistics. Gibbs, Raymond W. and Steen, Gerard J. (eds). Amsterdam / Phila-
13. delphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company. 47–56.
14. Boers, Frank. 2000. Metaphor awareness and vocabulary intention. Applied Linguistics.